

Precipitation of Lead Sulphate through Cation Replacement by Chromium

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Gravimetric determination of lead is usually carried out by precipitating its sulphate. As lead is associated with many other metal ions in alloys, catalysts etc., a simple and efficient technique such as homogeneous precipitation (HP) may be useful for its macro separation even if it takes a little longer time. The advantages of this technique are well established¹. Earlier, we have developed procedures for the analysis of lead in type metal successfully applying the HP technique². For analysing lead in multicomponent catalyst systems containing lead and chromium, slow release of lead from its EDTA complex in presence of sulphate by gradual displacement with chromium should be an ideal method. Preliminary investigations by us indicated the possibility of precipitating lead sulphate by this method, contrary to the findings of Newcomb and Markham³. This paper reports on the separation of lead as its sulphate through cation replacement by chromium.

Results and Discussion

Results show that in the range of 5–100 mg of lead, the deviation from the expected value is 0.1 or 0.2 mg only. However, the precipitate was always pale violet in colour due to the adsorption of small quantities of chromium(III)-EDTA complex. As the complex is completely converted to Cr_2O_3 below 500° with a weight-loss of 17.2%, the ignition of lead sulphate at 500° is expected to reduce any error resulting from the adsorption. Experiments were also carried out to precipitate lead upto 300 mg by the suggested procedure. The precipitate was dried at 120° for 2 h. The positive error was in the vicinity of 0.2 mg for 100 mg Pb but did not exceed 0.8 mg even for 300 mg of Pb.

Several type-metal samples containing (Pb, 70–75; Sb, 17–20; Sn, 8–10%) were analysed following the present method as well as by the classical method of separating lead sulphate by direct precipitation, dissolving the precipitate in acetic acid and titrating the lead with EDTA using xylenol orange as indicator. The results compare well and the present method gives highly reproducible results. Al^{III} , Cu^{II} , Sn^{II} , Sb^{III} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Mn^{II} and chloride did not interfere either individually or in combination in 50 mg/5–100 mg (in 60 ml) Pb range. One can analyse lead in pure, alloy and multicomponent solutions in spite of

adsorption of small quantities of chromium(III)-EDTA complex.

Experimental

All the reagents were of analytical grade. Aqueous solutions of 0.05, 0.025 and 0.001 M lead nitrate were used as source of lead ions. Aqueous solutions (10 mg ml⁻¹) of Al^{III} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} were prepared from their sulphates. Solutions of Sn and Sb (10 mg ml⁻¹) were prepared by dissolving the metal in a minimum amount of a 1:1 mixture of HNO_3 + HF and diluting with distilled water. Aqueous 0.2 M solutions of chromium and sulphate were prepared from their nitrate and ammonium salts. A 5% (w/v) aqueous solution of the disodium salt of EDTA was used for complexation.

Estimation in pure solutions: To a solution containing 5–100 mg of lead, were added EDTA (5 ml), ammonium sulphate (5 ml) and chromium(III) nitrate (4 ml) solutions. The solution was diluted to 60 ml and heated on a boiling water-bath. The precipitation started in 15 min and was complete after 90 min. Heating was continued until the volume was reduced to ~15 ml, which took about 2 h. The solution was then cooled for 30 min and the resulting precipitate was washed first with 1% H_2SO_4 and then with 50% ethanol until the washing was free from sulphate. The precipitate was dried at 80° for 30 min and ignited at 550° with usual precautions and weighed. Interference of Al^{III} , Cu^{II} , Sn^{II} , Sb^{III} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Fe^{III} and Mn^{II} in 50 mg concentrations each together or individually for 5–50 mg of lead was examined. Thus, the system contained approximately 5 or 50 mg of lead, 50 mg of the interfering metal ion, 10 ml of EDTA and 8 ml of chromium(III) nitrate. Interference of chloride ion was studied upto 2.5 times of NH_4Cl over 100 mg of lead.

Analysis of type-metal: The type-metal sample (~10 g) was dissolved in 1:1 mixture of HNO_3 + HF (30 ml), then nitrous fume removed by boiling for a few min and the solution was diluted to 1 dm³. To an aliquot (10 ml) of the solution were added solutions of EDTA (5 ml), ammonium sulphate (5 ml) and chromium(III) nitrate (4 ml), then diluted to 60 ml and heated on a boiling water-bath for over 2 h. The final volume was restricted to less than 20 ml to avoid solubility effects. The rest of the procedure followed was as above.

NOTES

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